

**TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA
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**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE METHOD OF SOCIALIZATION IN
TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

ABSTRACT

The modern demand of society in the Republic of Uzbekistan for competitive and highly qualified graduates who are able to function effectively at a new stage of development requires not only increasing the level of mass knowledge of a foreign language, but also stimulating the need to use it in educational, scientific and business spheres of life. The purpose of this article is to describe and analyze the experience of the formation of universal sociolinguistic and communicative competence through foreign language socialization of students of non-linguistic specialties in English-language discourse outside the natural language environment. The research methodology is based on a comparative analysis of the obtained data using a formalized closed questionnaire and statistical data processing. The competence-based approach makes it possible to widely apply varied methods of teaching and using English in a non-linguistic university, combined with a change in the principles of organizing the educational process, aimed at encouraging speech and social interaction. It is concluded that the tasks of foreign language socialization in the classroom differ from socialization in the natural language environment, which entails the need to expand the boundaries of modern linguodidactics, change

approaches to the very conditions of learning and communication in a foreign language in the learning process.

Keywords: foreign language socialization; sociolinguistic competence; communicative competence; competence-based approach; competitive learning environment; learning intensification; speech and social interaction.

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CHET TILINI O'QITISHDA SOTSIALIZATSIYA METODNING SAMARADORLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

O'zbekiston Respublikasida jamiyatning yangi rivojlanish bosqichida samarali faoliyat yurita oladigan, raqobatbardosh va yuqori malakali bitiruvchilarga bo'lgan zamonaviy talabi nafaqat chet tilini ommaviy bilish darajasini oshirish, balki undan hayotning ta'lim, ilmiy va biznes sohalarida foydalanish zaruriyatini ham taqozo etmoqda. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi tabiiy til muhitidan tashqari ingliz tilidagi nutqda nolingvistik mutaxassislik talabalarining chet tilini ijtimoiylashtirish orqali universal sotsiolingvistik va kommunikativ kompetentsiyalarini shakllantirish tajribasini tavsiflash va tahlil qilishdir. Tadqiqot metodologiyasi rasmiylashtirilgan yopiq so'rovnomalar va statistik ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash yordamida olingan ma'lumotlarni qiyosiy tahlil qilishga asoslangan. Kompetentsiyaga asoslangan yondashuv nutqni va ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sirni rag'batlantirishga qaratilgan o'quv jarayonini tashkil etish tamoyillarini o'zgartirish bilan birlashtirilgan holda, nolingvistik universitetda ingliz tilini o'qitish va undan foydalanishning turli usullarini keng qo'llash imkonini beradi. Sinfda chet tilini ijtimoiylashtirish vazifalari tabiiy til muhitidagi sotsializatsiyadan farq qiladi, bu zamonaviy lingvodidaktikaning chegaralarini kengaytirish, chet tilini o'rganish va muloqot qilish o'quv jarayoni sharoitlariga yondashuvni o'zgartirish zarurligini keltirib chiqaradi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tilining sotsializatsiyasi; sotsiolingvistik kompetentsiya; kommunikativ kompetentsiya; kompetentsiyaga asoslangan yondashuv; raqobatbardosh o'quv muhiti; o'rganish intensivligi; nutq va ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir

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ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ МЕТОДА ИНОЯЗЫЧНОЙ СОЦИАЛИЗАЦИИ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Современный спрос общества Республики Узбекистан на конкурентоспособных и высококвалифицированных выпускников, способных эффективно функционировать на новом этапе развития, требует не только повышения уровня массового владения иностранным языком, но и стимулирования потребности в его использовании. в образовательной, научной и деловой сферах жизни. Целью данной статьи является описание и анализ опыта формирования универсальной социолингвистической и коммуникативной компетенции посредством иноязычной социализации студентов неязыковых специальностей в англоязычном дискурсе вне естественной языковой среды. Методология исследования основана на сравнительном анализе полученных данных с использованием формализованной закрытой анкеты и статистической обработки данных. Компетентностный подход позволяет широко применять разнообразные методы обучения и использования английского языка в неязыковом вузе в сочетании с изменением принципов организации учебного процесса, направленных на поощрение речевого и социального взаимодействия. Делается вывод о том, что задачи иноязычной социализации на уроке отличаются от социализации в естественной языковой среде, что влечет за собой необходимость расширения границ современной лингводидактики, изменения подходов к самим условиям обучения и общения на иностранном языке в условиях процесс изучения.

Ключевые слова: иноязычная социализация; социолингвистическая компетентность; коммуникативная компетентность; компетентностный подход; конкурентная среда обучения; интенсификация обучения; речевое и социальное взаимодействие.

Introduction. The modern demand of society for highly qualified personnel capable of ensuring the innovative development of the country, being implemented in a new type of economy, integrating into the world community through

international cooperation and cooperation in various industries makes the problem of improving the level of English language proficiency of graduates for effective communication even more relevant.

A number of legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan [9; 10] spell out the need to form a universal communicative competence, including the ability to communicate in a foreign language for professional intercultural interaction in a multicultural environment. And in a number of resolutions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the task is to ensure the global competitiveness of education in our country until 2030, which is also difficult to solve without a significant improvement in the quality of mass foreign language training. The purpose of this scientific article is to describe and analyze the experience of the formation of universal sociolinguistic and communicative competence among non-linguistic students through foreign language socialization in the English-language professional discourse.

Literature review. Teaching English in the humanities, technical and natural sciences in the universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan is conducted, as a rule, in the conditions of classroom bilingualism within the concept of "English for Special Purposes" (ESP). It is considered proven that the mastery of ESP will not be effective without the simultaneous assimilation of the linguistic culture of the language being studied [1, 73] and foreign language socialization [2, 86], which is understood as the process of mastering new norms of speech behavior and ideas about a different culture after mastering the relevant standards of speech behavior in the native language [5, 600]. Foreign students go through such socialization while living in the country of the language being studied [6, 101]. Successful students, striving to gain access to equal social interaction with members of the host community, along with a foreign language, acquire a hybrid form of identity [1, 74], covering ethnic and linguistic cultures. The difficulties faced by students who are unsuccessful in terms of socialization are associated with the presence of a strong foreign accent [2, 87], communicative [2, 89] and sociocultural [2, 92] barriers, with a lack of identification with the culture of the host country [2, 94].

In this regard, attempts are being made to change the conditions for using a foreign language while studying outside the natural language environment. Thus, Chinese specialists teach English by immersion in a virtual foreign language world through computer network games [3, 2475], Japanese teachers use mobile phones and social networks [4, 156], however, such a combination of real and virtual communication does not provide joint productive activities and socialization.

Recently, more and more publications have begun to appear that popularize the modern experience of foreign language socialization for the formation of communicative competence among students in universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan [5; 6; 7; 8; 11; 12].

However, from the publications of colleagues, it becomes obvious that foreign-language socialization covers the already most prepared and motivated

students; data are not provided on how the applied approaches are reflected in the level of mass English language proficiency of groups of students of different levels of language competence, on their readiness to use the language outside the classroom.

Research problem. If we talk about the task of forming a full-fledged sociolinguistic and communicative competence through the assimilation of the norms of speech behavior and social interaction in the conditions of classroom bilingualism (quite typical for universities in the Republic of Uzbekistan), then most Western experts consider it difficult to accomplish. After all, the knowledge of how to choose the right communication tactics cannot be obtained without real experience of oral and written communication with a large number of different people from different social groups. Accordingly, it is objectively difficult to undergo such socialization outside the linguistic and social environment. Scientists agree that linguistic knowledge obtained in classrooms cannot ensure the formation of social competence, since it is closely related to certain socio-cultural contexts that are difficult to reproduce in the classroom. Therefore, the use of a foreign language is not perceived by students as a social practice, at least until they are in the country of the language being studied.

Research methodology. In this study, the methods of theoretical description, literature review and experiment were applied. The method of theoretical description was used in working with terminology, in describing the research problem, and also in the process of theoretical substantiation of some experimental results. The literature review helped to highlight the main aspects of the subject and object of our research, which were studied by the predecessors, as well as to identify untouched points in this problem.

The experiment was carried out on the basis of the Yangiyer branch of the Tashkent University of Chemical Technology, located in the city of Yangiyer (Republic of Uzbekistan). The principle of pragmatic integrativity was taken as the methodological basis of the experiment, combining the best of traditional methods and the latest teaching technologies.

Primary attention is paid to the competence-based approach and project-based learning activities with an emphasis on a significant increase in the amount of independent work of students (both individual and team) in the competitive environment of the university.

The experimental training format is implemented through a combination of classical English classes within the study group (with a constant set of communicators) with a system of regular events with a changing composition of participants, which is reflected in Table 1.

Table 1. The structure of teaching non-linguistic students through foreign language socialization

Structural elements of a foreign language learning environment			
Traditional	Activities for foreign language socialization		
Lesson	Contests	Olympiads	Open Examination
	Dramatization competition	Audition Olympiad. Lectures by native English speakers	Festival of professionally oriented films made by students
	Competition of digital stories on professional and socially significant topics (Digital Story Telling)	Machine Translation Editing Olympiad	Briefing on interdisciplinary topics
	CV and Cover Letter competition (as part of Academic Mobility)	Written Translation Olympiad	Debates on interdisciplinary topics
		Olympiad in the technique of speaking	Interdisciplinary conference

To monitor the impact of foreign language socialization of non-linguistic students in an innovative learning environment on reducing the degree of difficulties in communicating in English in various communicative situations and on the willingness to use it in their activities, a formalized closed questionnaire survey was conducted on the topic "English in my life". Program questions "How difficult is it for you to communicate in English in different situations?" and "What activities using the English language are you ready to take part in?" were given to two groups of respondents (n=120) aged 19 to 21 years.

The control group (CG) consisted of 60 students who studied for one semester (2021-2022 academic year) in the traditional mode in groups with a permanent teacher and student body. The experimental group (EG) included 60 students who studied during the same period in a simulated competitive foreign language environment with a variable set of communication participants and various situations of communication and social interaction. All students who took part in the surveys were tested before the start of the semester using the entrance standard testing: the level of English proficiency of the participants in the experiment at that time corresponded to the levels of Elementary and Low-Intermediate on the scale of the Association of European Testers (ALTE), which is generally the initial level language competence.

Research results. The results of the analysis of the received answers to the first question of the questionnaire are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Distribution of answers to the question "How difficult is it for you to communicate in English in different situations?" (in %)

	In class		With familiar bilinguals and native speakers		With unfamiliar bilinguals and native speakers	
	Mode 1 CG	Mode 2 EG	Mode 1 CG	Mode 2 EG	Mode 1 CG	Mode 2 EG
Extremely difficult	13	0	13	3	17	5
Difficult	27	17	42	20	47	25
Neutral	22	27	20	23	25	29
Easy	27	40	25	37	12	28
Too easy	12	17	0	17	0	13

Note: Mode 1 - traditional training with a constant set of participants and communicative situations; mode 2 - training in a competitive learning environment with a variable set of communicative partners and situations of communication and social interaction.

According to Table 2, depending on three typical situations of communication, the number of students experiencing difficulties of varying degrees of intensity after studying in the traditional mode ranges from 13% to 47%. From 12% to 27% of respondents, respectively, do not experience and do not experience difficulties at all.

The number of people experiencing various kinds of difficulties in foreign language communication in typical communicative situations after training in an experimental mode has noticeably decreased. From 3% to 25% of the respondents stated that they had various kinds of problems, which is noticeably less than in the groups who studied English traditionally. The number of students who do not experience difficulties compared to the first group of informants, on the contrary, has grown: from 13% to 40% of respondents noted that it is “not at all difficult” or “not difficult” for them to communicate in a foreign language in different circumstances.

To determine the level of need to use a foreign language, the same groups of respondents were asked the question: “In which of the following activities using English are you ready to take part?”.

Informants could choose an unlimited number of options: 1) conversation in English with foreigners; 2) watching documentaries on professionally oriented

topics; 3) reading articles and books in the specialty; 4) correspondence with bilinguals/native speakers; 5) maintaining your own blog in English on professional topics; 6) creation of films/rollers/media product; 7) presentation at conferences with reports; 8) is not ready yet. The distribution of students' answers is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Distribution of answers to the question “Which of the following activities using English are you ready to take part in?”

According to Figure 1, students who studied traditionally, in general, choose 2.5 times fewer types of activities in English (109 answers in total) than students who went through experimental training (280 answers, respectively), giving preference to passive types of activities such as like "reading", "watching video". The number of those wishing to make a report, maintain their own blog was small. At the same time, the choice of answers by students who have gone through training using a competency-based approach and the principles of foreign language socialization differs quantitatively and qualitatively. Thus, the number of students who are ready to engage in not only passive, but also active activities in a foreign language has increased markedly: on average, the number of people who want to talk and correspond with foreigners, watch English-language films, read articles and books has doubled. In addition, the number of students who strive to perform complex types of professional and academic activities has significantly increased: on average, the number of those able to prepare a report and make a media product

has increased by 5 times, and blogging by 8 times. The number of those who are not ready to use English has more than halved. The distribution of answers to the second question of the questionnaire generally correlates with the distribution of answers to the first question: the less difficulties students experience in English-speaking communication, the more they acquire the need not only to communicate in the language, but also to use it to solve practical problems.

The discussion of the results. The analysis of the obtained results confirms that after only one semester of training in the experimental mode, students subjectively experience significantly less difficulties in communicating in English both with members of the study group and with familiar and unfamiliar native speakers and bilinguals than students who studied in the traditional mode. which is not only confirmed by an increase in the desire to speak English, but also indicates a decrease in barriers that prevented communication. The number of students who prefer not only passive but also active activities in English is noticeably increasing, including the number of those wishing to perform complex activities.

This signals the emergence of the need for most of the subjects to both communicate in English and actively use it in the process of individual or joint activities, which indicates a foreign language socialization. During a free-form survey, students assessed the new mode of study as follows: “a very productive and modern format”, “much more interesting and useful than studying from a textbook”, “there was a desire to speak”, “there is a noticeable progress”, “there is more self-confidence and one’s own abilities”, “interest in the language has appeared”, “a good incentive for further learning the language”, “you begin to believe in yourself that you can master the language to the required degree and use it in your life”.

Foreign language socialization creates conditions under which all students not only have equal opportunities to compare their level of communicative competence, but are also forced to discuss with students from other groups in the stressful situation of an exam in the format of a debate or briefing, answer questions from strangers with different levels of language proficiency, make presentations to an unfamiliar audience, present and defend group projects. This learning mode allows you to implement a competency-based approach and the principles of collaborative pedagogy, as well as significantly increase the intensity of the process of learning and using the English language in a competitive environment that stimulates speech and social interaction. Students go through not only different stages of the formation and improvement of sociolinguistic and communicative competence, but also the corresponding stages of foreign language socialization in professional discourse, including outside their study group.

Conclusion. The newest tasks of learning a foreign language are not only mastering the ways of communication in this language within the boundaries of other cultures, but also gaining experience in using the language in social activities. And although it seems obvious that foreign language socialization when learning a language outside the natural language environment has a number of serious

limitations, it is necessary to no lesser extent than when mastering a language in the country of its native speakers. However, the goal and objectives of this type of socialization initially differ from socialization in the language environment, which entails the need to expand the boundaries of modern linguodidactics, change approaches to the very conditions of learning and communication in a foreign language in the educational process.

The active application of the competency-based approach in the competitive learning environment of a university with a change in the principles of organizing the educational process opens up a wide range of opportunities for increasing the effectiveness of mass teaching a foreign language in classroom bilingualism, when there are no natural conditions for diverse communication and foreign language socialization, which is possible only through social interaction with different students. communicative partners as a result of joint productive activities in the target language. New approaches allow you to create a variety of communicative situations with a variable composition of communicants, significantly increase the intensity of communication and cooperation, which makes it possible to more successfully form universal communicative competence in a larger number of students, stimulating their need to actively use the English language and motivating them to study it in depth.

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